

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE FEMOFLOR TEST IN ASSESSING THE STATE OF VAGINAL MICROBIOCENOSIS IN PRETERM VAGINAL DISCHARGE

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Annatation. Among the problems of modern obstetrics and pediatrics, premature birth occupies one of the main places. But premature discharge of the amniotic fluid is one of the main reasons for premature labor. Amniotic fluid plays an important role in the biomechanics of childbirth and is of great physiological importance for the state of the fetus, because the amniotic fluid creates conditions for the free development and movement of the fetus, and also protects the developing fetus from negative effects.

Key words: Premature discharge of amniotic fluid, premature babies, preterm birth, genital tract biocenosis, vaginal microbiocenosis.

The purpose of the study is to determine the qualitative and quantitative composition of microorganisms that make up the microbiocenosis of the genital tract in pregnant women with premature discharge using PCR.

Research materials and methods. Vaginal swabs of 28 pregnant women who came to the perinatal center of Bukhara region before the period of 26-34 weeks and 24-36 years of age were studied. The control group consisted of 11 pregnant women aged 24-36 with a physiologically developing pregnancy of 20-25 weeks. We used the Femoflor-16 test to study the biocenosis of the urogenital tract in women. Quantitative evaluation of vaginal microflora was carried out both in absolute and relative terms. The absolute indicator is the amount of DNA of the desired microorganism in the sample, expressed in GE, expressed as a decimal logarithm - lg. The relative quantitative indicator of the microorganism was

calculated as the ratio of the amount of the desired microorganism to the amount of the total bacterial mass. It is presented in two formats: the decimal log difference of the number of the respective group of microorganisms and the total bacterial mass and as a percentage of the total bacterial mass.

Research results. Normocenosis was found in 10 cases of women with premature amniocentesis. Among them, only 1 patient was diagnosed with absolute normocytosis, and in the rest, 8 out of 9 cases had conditional normocytosis with fungi of the genus *Ureaplasma (urealyticum + parvum)* and *Candida spp.* In 1 case, the titer was more than 10^4 and 10^3 , respectively. Anaerobic dysbiosis was detected on average in 7 (25%) women with premature amniotic fluid. 24-70% of the total bacterial mass in cervical smears of patients was *Lactobacillus spp.* organizes. *Eubacterium spp.* It was detected in high titers in 2 pregnant women. A combination of anaerobic bacteria and microorganisms associated with bacterial vaginosis was found in 5 cases. Normocenosis was found in 10 out of 11 cases (90.9%) in physiologically developing women of pregnancy. Of them, absolute normocenosis was observed in 4 women, conditional normocenosis in 6 women. Among women with conditional normocenosis, *Ureaplasma (urealyticum + parvum)* was detected in 4 cases, fungi belonging to the *Candida* genus were detected in 1 patient, and both pathogens were detected in diagnostic titers in 1 pregnant woman. Severe anaerobic dysbiosis with a physiologically developing pregnancy from 11 pregnant women It was found in 1. The etiological structure is represented by the following pathogens: *Gardnerella vaginalis/Prevotella bivia/Porp Streptococcus spp.*, *Gardnerella hyromonas spp.*, *Eubacterium spp.*, *Atopobium vaginae*, *Ureaplasma (urealyticum+parvum)*.

Summary. In women with physiological pregnancy, lactobacilli decreased by only 9.1% ($p=0.002$), in most cases normocytosis was detected. Anaerobic microorganisms (14 out of 28 or 50%) played the main role in the structure of dysbiosis in pregnant women with premature amniocentesis: *Gardnerella vaginalis* (17.8%), *Candida spp. genus fungi* (10.7%), *Ureaplasma (urealyticum + parvum)* -

17.8%, *Atopobium vaginae* (7.1%). *Aerobic dysbiosis* was noted only in 2 women (7.1%), *Streptococcus spp.* and *Candida spp. fungi* of the genus, mixed - observed in 2 (7.1%) cases. The identified facts confirm the point of view about the important role of bacterial vaginosis in the genesis of premature birth, emphasize the need to diagnose dysbiosis in the restoration of normal microflora.